

Local Anaesthetics. Part—II¹ : Synthesis of 2-(N,N-Disubstituted Aminoacetamido)-4-*p*-Fluorophenyl and -*m*-Methoxyphenyl Thiazoles

P. N. BHARGAVA, RAM LAKHAN* and RAMACHARYA TRIPATHI**

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

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Thirteen new 2-(N,N-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-*p*-fluorophenyl and -*m*-methoxyphenyl thiazoles have been synthesised. Hydrochlorides of these compounds have been screened for their local anaesthetic activity by Frog's sciatic plexus method and the activity compared with that of procaine hydrochloride. Of these, 2-piperidinoacetamido-4-*p*-fluorophenylthiazole-HCl is the most potent; nearly 15 times in terms of onset of anaesthesia in comparison with procaine-HCl.

MARKS and Rubin² have claimed that chloro-procaine (1), (β -diethylaminoethyl 4-amino-2-chlorobenzoate) exhibits local anaesthetic activity comparable to that of procaine. Moreover, chloro-procaine is systemically less toxic due to its fast metabolic hydrolysis³.

It has also been observed that the duration of anaesthesia and topical anaesthetic properties of procaine-like compounds are favoured by an increase of the aminoalkyl group and the intermediate alkylene chain. Thus, the dibutyl homologue butacaine, 3-dibutylaminopropyl 4-aminobenzoate⁴, in which both the size of the N-alkyl groups and chain length are enlarged, is found to be nearly as active topically as cocaine⁵. Recently Takman *et al*⁶ have reported that 2-(*t*-butylamino)-2',6'-propionoxylidide (2), a lidocaine homologue, has significantly long lasting local anaesthetic activity and sufficiently low acute toxicity.

2-amino-4-arylthiazoles were treated with chloroacetyl chloride in dry benzene to give the corresponding 2-chloroacetamido-4-arylthiazoles. Reaction of these compounds with different secondary amines in absolute ethanol yielded 2-(N,N-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-arylthiazoles (Table 1). The hydrochlorides of these bases were prepared by usual methods (Table 2) and evaluated for conduction anaesthesia on frogs by the sciatic plexus method¹⁰.

Experimental

All melting points were observed with a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried out on a Coleman analyser. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 grating spectrophotometer as nujol mulls and nmr on a Varian-A60D spectrometer at the probe temperature (44.5°) as CCl₄ or

(1)

(2)

(3)

where X = *p*-F or *m*-CH₃O.

Taking these facts into consideration and that the 2-aminothiazole derivatives^{7,8} exhibit marked local anaesthetic activity, the authors have synthesised a series of fluorine and methoxy substituted 4-phenyl-2-(N,N-disubstituted aminoacetamido)thiazoles having the general formula (3).

2-Amino-4-*p*-fluorophenyl- and 2-amino-4-*m*-methoxyphenylthiazoles were prepared by the condensation of *p*-fluoroacetophenone or *m*-methoxyacetophenone with thiourea and iodine following a slightly modified method of Joshi and Bahel⁹. The

CDCl₃ solutions using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G (E. Merck).

2-Amino-4-*p*-fluorophenylthiazole : It was prepared from *p*-fluoroacetophenone by a slightly modified procedure of Joshi and Bahel⁹. The unreacted iodine was removed by washing with aqueous sodium thiosulphate and the product crystallised (EtOH), m.p. 120° (lit⁹. m.p. 120°).

2-Amino-4-*m*-methoxyphenylthiazole : It was prepared as above in 68% yield by reaction of *m*-methoxy-

* To whom correspondence should be addressed.

** Present address : Department of Chemistry, Udai Pratap (P. G.) College, Varanasi (U.P.).

acetophenone, thiourea and iodine and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 127° (Found : N, 13.8 ; S, 15.8. C₁₀H₁₀N₂OS requires N, 13.6 ; S, 15.5%).

2-Chloroacetamido-4-p-fluorophenylthiazole : To an ice-cooled solution of 2-amino-4-p-fluorophenylthiazole (9.5 g) in dry benzene (60 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (4 ml) dissolved in dry benzene (30 ml) was added slowly with vigorous shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 3 hr. Benzene was distilled off and the residue treated with 5% NaHCO₃ solution to remove unreacted chloroacetyl chloride. The product was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 80%, m.p. 135° (Found : N, 10.5 ; Cl, 13.3. C₁₁H₈ClFN₂OS requires N, 10.3 ; Cl, 13.1%). IR : 3220m, 1730s, 1580s, 1240s cm⁻¹.

Likewise, 2-chloroacetamido-4-m-methoxyphenylthiazole was prepared. It was crystallised from ethanol, yield 75%, m.p. 145° (Found : N, 9.8 ; Cl, 12.3. C₁₂H₁₁ClN₂O₂S requires N, 9.9 ; Cl, 12.6%). IR : 3300m, 1680s, 1590s, 1260s cm⁻¹.

2-Piperidinoacetamido-4-p-fluorophenylthiazole : A mixture of 2-chloroacetamido-4-p-fluorophenylthiazole (2.0 g), piperidine (1.0 ml), absolute ethanol (40 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.0 g) was heated under reflux on a water bath for 8 hr. The excess of amine and ethanol was removed by distillation and the residue was treated with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove acid impurities. It was crystallised from absolute ethanol, yield 70%, m.p. 152° (Found : C, 60.3 ; H, 5.4 ; N, 13.3. C₁₆H₁₆FN₂OS requires C, 60.2 ; H, 5.6 ; N, 13.2%). IR : 3200w (N-H stretch), 1710s (C=O stretch), 1580s, 1510m, 1300s, 1250m cm⁻¹. NMR (CDCl₃) δ 6.95-8.20 (m, 5H, aromatic protons), 3.21 (s, 2H, -COCH₂-N<), 2.33-2.75 (resonance signals for 2' and 6' protons of the piperidine ring), 1.15-2.0 (resonance signals for 3', 4' and 5' protons of the piperidine ring), 9.80 (br, 1H, -NH-) ppm.

Similarly, other 2-(N,N-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-p-fluorophenyl- and -4-m-methoxyphenylthiazoles were prepared by the reaction of different acyclic and cyclic secondary amines with 2-chloroacetamido-4-p-fluorophenylthiazole and 2-chloroacetamido-4-m-methoxyphenylthiazole separately. These were crystallised from ethanol. Their characterization data are given in Table 1. The ir and nmr spectral data of compounds No. 1, 5, 6 and 12 were typical of the structures assigned to them.

Hydrochloride of 2-piperidinoacetamido-4-p-fluorophenylthiazole : A solution of 2-piperidinoacetamido-4-p-fluorophenylthiazole (2.0 g) prepared in anhydrous benzene was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. A solid mass was formed which was filtered and washed with dry ether. The crude product was crystallised from absolute ethanol, yield 80%, m.p. 252° (Found : C, 54.2 ; H, 5.2 ; N, 12.2 ; Cl, 9.7. C₁₆H₁₆ClFN₂OS requires C, 54.0 ; H, 5.4 ; N, 11.8 ; Cl, 10.0%).

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF 2-(N,N-DISUBSTITUTED AMINOACETAMIDO)-4-ARYLTHIAZOLES (3)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Formula
X = p-F					
1.	Et	Et	65	110	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ FN ₂ OS
2.	Pr	Pr	70	259	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ FN ₂ OS
3.	i-Pr	i-Pr	72	273	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ FN ₂ OS
4.	n-Bu	n-Bu	65	283	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ FN ₂ OS
5.	i-Bu	i-Bu	80	141	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ FN ₂ OS
6.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	80	115	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ FN ₂ OS
7.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	75	182	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ FN ₂ OS
8.	Piperidino		70	152	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ FN ₂ OS
9.	Pyrrolidino		70	103	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ FN ₂ OS
X = m-CH ₃ O					
10.	i-Bu	i-Bu	70	156	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
11.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	72	116	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
12.	Piperidino		75	112	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S
13.	Pyrrolidino		65	118	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S

Satisfactory C, H and N analyses were obtained.

Following the above procedure, hydrochlorides of other 2-(N,N-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-p-fluorophenyl- and -4-m-methoxyphenylthiazoles were prepared. Their yields and melting points are recorded in Table 2. Satisfactory N and Cl analyses of the hydrochlorides were obtained.

Pharmacological screening for plexus anaesthesia on frogs : The base hydrochlorides reported in Table 2 were screened for their local anaesthetic activity on frogs at 0.1% concentration of the compounds in 0.7% saline adopting the procedure of Bulbring and Wajda¹⁰. Three frogs were tested for each of the compounds and the average time of onset of anaesthesia was recorded. The results (Table 2) are compared with that of procaine hydrochloride used as the standard.

TABLE 2—LOCAL ANAESTHETIC ACTIVITY OF 2-(N,N-DISUBSTITUTED AMINOACETAMIDO)-4-ARYLTHIAZOLES HYDROCHLORIDES

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Onset of anaesthesia (in minutes)*	
					0.05N	0.1N
X = p-F						
1.	Et	Et	60	142	0.50	0.55
2.	Pr	Pr	68	256	2.20	2.45
3.	i-Pr	i-Pr	70	162	1.55	2.20
4.	n-Bu	n-Bu	72	181	1.10	1.20
5.	i-Bu	i-Bu	75	135	1.05	1.10
6.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	72	173	0.40	0.50
7.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	70	166	0.45	0.50
8.	Piperidino		80	252	0.30	0.35
9.	Pyrrolidino		60	156	0.35	0.40
X = m-CH ₃ O						
10.	i-Bu	i-Bu	65	140	10.00	11.00
11.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	75	165	9.15	10.30
12.	Piperidino		75	260	6.10	6.45
13.	Pyrrolidino		60	175	7.00	8.15
	Procaine Hydrochloride †				8.25	9.45

* Onset of anaesthesia in minutes after administration of anaesthetic, detected by using HCl of given normality ;

† Procaine hydrochloride (at 0.1% concentration) was used as such, as the standard.

Results and Discussion

From the screening results it is concluded that all the hydrochlorides of 2-(N,N-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-*p*-fluorophenylthiazoles are considerably more effective in producing onset of anaesthesia in frogs in comparison to procaine hydrochloride. Of these, 2-piperidinoacetamido-4-*p*-fluorophenylthiazole is the most potent local anaesthetic. The activity of different groups in hydrophilic moiety lies in the order : piperidino > pyrrolidino > benzyl > ethyl > isobutyl > *n*-butyl > isopropyl > *n*-propyl. But the hydrochlorides of 2-(N,N-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-*m*-methoxyphenylthiazoles require more or less the same time for the onset of anaesthesia as the standard.

It is also apparent that significantly quick response of the compounds No. 1-9 (in Table 2) to produce onset of anaesthesia is due to the presence of 4-*p*-fluorophenyl substituent. It is also interesting to note that 4-*p*-fluorophenylthiazole derivatives reported here are much more potent local anaesthetics than the substituted benzothiazole derivatives described in an earlier communication¹.

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